

Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in relation to Gender and Academic Qualification in Gaya District

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Abstract

Teachers are the main pillars of any educational system. Teacher's job satisfaction create effective climate in the school. The present study was to find out the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. The investigator compared the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers with respect to gender, educational qualification and professional qualification. Descriptive survey method was adopted to conduct the study. 120 sample were collected from 15 government school teachers of Gaya District. Finding revealed that graduate male and female teachers are more satisfied with their job rather than professionally qualified teachers. Result also indicates that female teachers who have M.Sc. / M.A., B.Ed. degree are more satisfied than professionally qualified teachers.

Keywords : Job Satisfaction, Secondary School teachers, Education Qualification.

INTRODUCTION

India has a long tradition of learning and education has always been valued. Accordingly, education has been assigned high priority in the national development strategy and conscious efforts have been

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made towards the massive expansion of educational facilities in the country. In absolute terms, the educational system created in the country is vast when viewed in respect of the number of institutions, students and teachers and the variety of educational activity. However, effective utilization and success of educational set-up to produce quality output has been a subject matter of concern. Several commissions and committees who examined the functioning of educational set-up in the country have expressed concern about the quality, job satisfaction and work motivation of teachers towards an overall improvement of the education system.

The Education Commission (1964-66) observed, "The destiny of a nation is being shaped in her classrooms" and that 'as is the teacher, so is the nation' to emphasize about the importance of the teachers. The commission further observed that all the different factors which influence the quality of education and its contribution towards national development, the quality, competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant. The National Policy of Education (1986) recognized the crucial role of teachers and stated that the status of teacher reflects the socio-cultural ethos of a society. It further expressed that no people can rise above the level of its teachers and the government and the community should endeavour to create conditions which will help, motivate and inspire teachers on constructive and creative lines.

Weasmer and Woods (2004) also argue that teacher satisfaction reduces attrition, enhances collegiality between and among superiors, teachers, students and parents, improves job performance, and has an impact on student outcomes. Satisfied teachers are committed and motivated to do what is expected of them.

According to Johnson (2007), motivated and satisfied teachers are the primary contributors to a positive academic environment, and therefore, this has a high premium, among others, for maintaining quality in the education system. Motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn in the classroom, to warrant the implementation of educational reforms and progressive legislation, and will result in feelings of satisfaction and fulfilment.

A number of studies have been done on the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in relation to factors that is age, teaching, experience, marital status and school factors like working condition, nature of nature of administration etc. But in the present study, the researcher has decided to take some other factors. The main purpose of the study is to know problem of secondary school teacher in relation to gender and academic qualification.

Need and Importance of the Study

Teachers are the tools and provider of tools and the world for the children to develop into responsible citizen. For the success of an educational system, teacher plays an important role, which determines the quality of education and its contribution to national development. The progress and advancement of a country depends upon the quality of its teachers. Teachers is one the foundation stone in any system of education. The study of job satisfaction is a major research activity throughout world in all walks of organizational life including education. Every individual needs job to fulfil basic needs. It shares in strengthening the financial basis for individuals' lifestyle. Therefore, the job satisfaction is a most interesting field for many researchers.

Job satisfaction of the teachers should be the top priority of all organizations to achieve the desired goals of the institution. Research focusing specially on job satisfaction for secondary school teachers

identified several indicators of satisfaction and dissatisfaction. It is assumed that job satisfaction has dual role as a contributing aspect to commitment and as a prevailing variable that mediates the demographic and organizational determinants with commitment.

Statement of the Problem

Today, job satisfaction is the major concern for making teaching learning process effective. At present in our country most of the teacher works in a condition that creates frustration, anxiety and stress among them. Job Satisfaction is the key sources to improve the quality of education.

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Objective of the Study

1. To study the Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.
2. To compare the job satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers with respect to gender, educational qualifications and professional qualifications.

Hypothesis of Study

1. There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers.
2. There is no significant impact of academic qualifications and professional qualifications on the job satisfaction level of male and female secondary school teachers.

Delimitation of the Study

The study was limited to only 15 government secondary schools, situated in Gaya District.

Method

Descriptive survey method was adopted to conduct the study. In the present study, job satisfaction has been taken as the dependent variable, whereas variables such as gender, and academic qualifications constituted the independent variables.

Population and Sample

Population of the study consisted of all the government secondary schools of Gaya district of Bihar. From the district fifteen schools were randomly selected and all the teachers of these secondary schools were participant of the study. Sixty male and sixty female teachers were participant of the study. Care was taken to take equal number of male and female teachers for the study.

Tools used

Job Satisfaction Scale by Dr. Pramod Kumar and Prof. D.N.Mutha (year) was used to assess the Job Satisfaction of teachers.

Statistical technique

In order to analyse the raw data as per the objectives, suitable statistical techniques like mean, S.D. and t-test has been applied.

Analysis and interpretation

1. To find the significant difference in the job satisfaction secondary of school male and female teachers.

Table No. 1

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
Male	60	18.7	4.52	118	0.0193	Not Significant
Female	60	17.1	5.36			

The Table No. 1 reveals that the t- value (0.0193) is less than the table value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, value is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the job satisfaction between male and female secondary school teachers.

- To find the significant difference between graduate and post-graduate secondary school teachers on the job satisfaction level.**

Table No. 2

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
B.Sc. /B.A.-B.Ed.	10	20.5	2.36	38	0.649	Not Significant
M.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	30	19.5	4.64			

The Table No. 2 reveals that the t- value (0.649) is less than the table value (2.02) at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, t-value is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the job satisfaction between graduate and Post-graduate secondary school teachers.

- To find the significant difference in male secondary school teachers between post-graduation and professional qualified.**

Table No. 3

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
M.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	30	19.5	4.64	48	0.75	Not significant
Professional Qualification	20	16.6	4.55			

The Table No. 3 reveals that the t- value(0.75) is less than the table value (2.01) at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, t-test value is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the job satisfaction between Post- graduate and Professional qualified secondary school male.

4. To find the significant difference in male secondary school teachers between graduate qualification and professional qualified.

Table No. 4

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
M.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	10	20.5	2.36	28	2.43	Significant
Professional Qualification	20	16.6	4.55			

The Table No. 4 reveals that the t- value(2.43) is greater than table value (2.05) at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore t-value is significant. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. So it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction between graduate and Professional qualified secondary school male teachers. The result indicates that those teachers who are graduate, have more job satisfaction than their counter parts.

5. **To find out significant difference between female secondary school teachers with regards to their graduation qualification and professional qualification.**

Table No-5

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
B.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	9	20	1.57	43	0.857	Not Significant
M.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	36	18.56	4.61			

The table no. 5 reveals that the t-value (0.857) is less than table value (2.02) at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, t-value is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction between graduate and Post-graduate secondary school female teachers.

6. **To find out significant difference between female secondary school teachers with regards to their post-graduation qualification and professional qualification.**

Table No. 6

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
M.Sc. /M.A.-B.Ed.	36	18.56	4.61	49	7.66	Significant
Professional Qualification	15	11.2	4.29			

The table no. 6 reveals that the t-values (7.66) is greater than table value (2.68) at 0.01 level. So t-value is significant. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. So it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction between Post-graduate and Professional qualified secondary school female teachers.

7. To find out significant difference between female secondary school teachers with regards to their graduation qualification and professional qualification.

Table No. 7

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	Remark
B.Sc. /B.A.-B.Ed.	9	20	1.57	22	5.94	Significant
Professional Qualification	15	11.2	4.29			

The table no.7 reveals that the t-value(5.94) is greater than table value (2.82) at 0.01 level. So t-value is significant. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. So it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction between graduate and Professional qualified secondary school female teachers.

Result : Secondary school male teachers having graduate degree are more satisfied with their job rather than those who are professionally qualified. In the same way, female secondary school teachers who are having post graduate degree are more satisfied rather than those who are professionally qualified. Results also indicates that female graduate teachers having more job satisfaction in comparison to professionally qualified teachers.

Education Implication :

The present study will have implication for educational administrators, teachers, teacher educators and school personals. Teacher is the changing agent, leader, philosopher friend, But unless the teacher has mental health, unless s/he is free from worries, tensions and unless he is not satisfied in his job, he cannot discharge his/her duty effectively. Therefore, mental health, working condition, job satisfaction are pre-requisite for better functioning in the school.

Conclusion :

Job satisfaction among school teachers has been considered as a vital factor for the improvement of the education system.

Satisfaction is a psychological phenomenon and its concept is highly intricate and subjective. Job satisfaction describes how content an individual with his or her job. It expresses the extent of match between the employees' expectations from the job and the rewards that the job provides. Teacher's job satisfaction is one of the key factors in school dynamics and is generally considered as a primary dependent variable in terms of which effectiveness of the school is evaluated. his/ her pupils. The present study highlights the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers irrespective of gender and academic qualification. Study reveals that female graduate and post graduate teachers are more satisfied rather than professionally qualified teachers.

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